

Effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge regarding complementary therapies for labour pain among Nurses in selected hospital

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Abstract

Introduction: Labour pain is the painful sensation experienced during childbirth and this pain varies greatly and it is subjective for each person. Many mothers do not prefer to go for the invasive and pharmacological methods of pain relief in labour and seek complementary therapies for the very minimal side effects for both the mother and the baby and easy to take.

Objectives: To determine the effectiveness of structured teaching program regarding complementary therapies for labor pain among staff Nurses.

Material and Methods: A evaluative approach one group pre and posttest design were used, the study was conducted in a selected hospital at Punjab.30 Nurses were selected by using simple random sampling technique. Data was collected with the use of structured knowledge questionnaire. Pretest was collected and structured teaching plan on complementary therapies for labour pain was administered to staff Nurses. After 15 days the post test was conducted and data was analyzed. The result of the study revealed that in pretest 25(83.33%) of Nurses had inadequate knowledge, 05 (16.6) had moderate. Post test result revealed that out of 30 Nurses 10(33.33%) nurses had moderate knowledge, 20(66.66%) had adequate knowledge and no one had inadequate knowledge. While comparing knowledge between pretest and posttest the difference mean value was 9.90 with a standard deviation of 4.49 and calculated t value was 12.05.It was statistically significant at $P<0.05$ level.

Conclusion: Hence the structured teaching program is effective in imparting the knowledge on complementary therapies for labour pain among staff nurses.

Keywords: Knowledge; Effectiveness; Staff Nurses; Complementary Therapies; Labour Pain

1. Introduction

Labour is the active process of delivering a fetus and is characterized by regular, painful uterine contractions which increase in frequency and intensity [1] [2]. Environment also can influence pain perception in several ways. The appearance of the birthing facility the amount of noise and light, The temperature of the room, and the amount of space and equipment in the room contribute to the degree of strangers of the environment. Another important aspects of the environment is the philosophy of care and practice policies of the providers and moreover a positive approach can help to decrease pain perception [3].The pattern of labour pain is differs between nulliparous and multiparous women and it is well documented that pain scores are higher in the nulliparous as compared to the multiparous woman. Many mothers do not prefer to go for the invasive and pharmacological methods of pain relief in labour and seek complementary therapies for the very minimal side effects for both the mother and the baby and easy to take.[5] [6] .

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Objectives

- To assess the level of knowledge regarding complementary therapies for labor pain among staff nurses
- To determine the effectiveness of structured teaching program regarding complementary therapies for labor pain among staff nurses
- To find an association between the posttest level of knowledge regarding complementary therapies for labor pain among staff nurses and with their demographic variables

2. Materials and methods

- Research Approach: Quantitative Approach
- Research Design: Pre- experimental one group pretest posttest research design
- Setting of the study: Selected hospital at Punjab
- Population: Staff Nurses
- Sample: Staff Nurses working in the selected hospital
- Sampling Technique: Non-Probability Convenient Sampling

2.1. Inclusion criteria

The staff nurses who were willing to participate in the study.

The staff Nurse who were available at the time of data collection.

2.2. Exclusion criteria

The staff Nurse who were working in the emergency department

2.3. Tools and technique

The tool consists of two parts, namely:

- Part A: Socio-demographic data
- Part B: Structured knowledge Questions regarding complementary therapies for labor pain.

2.3.1. Part A: Socio-demographic data

Demographic variable includes age in years, professional qualification in Nursing, monthly income, designation, experience, previous exposure to education program regarding complementary therapy for labor pain.

2.3.2. Part B

This part has 26 questions regarding selected complementary therapies for labour pain and it's divided into 4 sections

Section A

Section	Description
Section A	General concept of complementary therapies for labour pain
Section B	Physical method of complementary therapies for labour pain
Section C	biological method of complementary therapies for labour pain
Section D	Psychological method of complementary therapies for labour pain

- Testing of the tool
- Validity of the tool

The prepared tool and content of the structured teaching program were sent to experts. The experts were requested to give their opinion to the appropriateness, accuracy and relevance of the items of the tool and structured teaching content in terms of strongly agree, agree and disagree.

The recommendation and suggestions of experts were considered to modify the items of tool as well as the content of structured teaching program.

2.3.3. Reliability of the tool

In order to establish the reliability of the tool, it was administered to four Nurses .reliability was obtained by split half technique. Reliability of the tool was found highly significant and reliable

Educational intervention program includes various complementary therapies like hydro therapy, therapeutic touch & massage, acupressure reflexology, aromatherapy, music therapy, relaxation and yoga. And its uses, suitability to receive complementary therapy and its complications.

2.4. Data collection procedure

The main study was conducted in a selected hospital of Punjab, formal approval was obtained from the concerned authority prior to the study.

The thirty Nurses were selected for the study by convenient sampling technique. Willingness of the Nurses was obtained with consent form. After the self-introduction the investigator explained the purpose of the study and requested to answer for the structured questionnaire after that education intervention program was conducted to staff nurses regarding complementary therapies for labour pain. Post-test was done after 15 days with the same questionnaire. Collected data was analyzed by using differential and inferential statistics and the result was interpreted

3. Results

Table 1 Distribution of demographic variables of the Nurses

S.No	Demographic variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
1	Age in years	21-30	05	16.66%
		31-40	10	33.33%
		41-50	10	33.33%
		Above 50	05	16.66%
2	Professional qualification in Nursing	A.N.M	05	16.66%
		G.N.M	13	43.66%
		B.Sc	11	36.66%
		M.Sc	01	03.66%
3	Monthly income	a)less than Rs.5000	06	20.00%
		b)Rs.5001 to Rs.10000	17	56.00%
		c)Rs.10001 to Rs.15000	05	16.66%
		d) above Rs.15001	02	06.66%
4	Designation	a) female ward assistant	05	16.66%
		b) staff nurse	17	56.66%
		c) ward in charge	06	20.00%
		d) nursing supervisor	02	06.00%
5	Experience	1 to 5 years	05	16.66%
		6 to 10 years	18	60.00%
		More than 10 years	07	23.33%
6	Previous exposure	Yes	02	06.66%

to continuing education programme regarding complementary therapies for labour pain	No	28	93.33%
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Table 2 Distribution of the level of knowledge regarding selected complementary therapies for labour pain among Nurses during pre test

S.No.	Level of knowledge	Pretest	
		Frequency	Percentage
1	Inadequate knowledge	25	83.33
2	Moderately adequate knowledge	05	16.33
3	Adequate knowledge	0	0

Table 3 Distribution of the level of knowledge regarding selected complementary therapies for labour pain among Nurses during post test

S.No.	Level of knowledge	Pretest	
		Frequency	Percentage
1	Inadequate knowledge	00	0
2	Moderately adequate knowledge	10	33.33
3	Adequate knowledge	20	66.66

Table 4 Comparison of the level of knowledge between pretest and post test.

S.No.	Classification of knowledge	Mean difference	Standard deviation	Standard error of the mean	't' test value & p value
1.	General concept of complementary	3.06	1.92	0.35	t = 8.70 P < 0.05(S)
2	Physical method of complementary therapies for labour pain	2.20	1.15	0.21	t = 10.41 P < 0.05(S)
3	biological method of complementary therapies for labour pain	2.40	1.10	0.20	t = 11.93 P < 0.05(S)
4	Psychological method of complementary therapies for labour pain	2.16	0.98	0.17	t = 12.04 P < 0.05(S)
	Total	9.90	4.49	0.82	t = 12.05 P < 0.05(S)

Table 5 Association between the post test level of knowledge of Nurses with the demographic variables

S.No	Demographic variables	Level of knowledge			Chi square values & p values
		Inadequate	Moderately adequate	Adequate	
1	Age in years a) 21-30 b) 31-40 c) 41-50 d) Above 50	- - - -	02 02 03 03	03 08 07 02	2.55 P>0.05 (N.S)
2	Professional qualification in Nursing a) A.N.M b) G.N.M c) B.Sc d) M.Sc	- - - -	04 03 03 00	01 10 08 01	06.19 P>0.05 (N.S)
3	Monthly income a) less than Rs.5000 b) Rs.5001 to Rs.10000 c) Rs.10001 to Rs.15000 d) above Rs.15000	- - - -	03 05 02 00	03 12 03 02	1.96 P>0.05 (N.S)
4	Designation a) female ward assistant b) staff nurse c) ward in charge d) nursing supervisor	- - - -	04 05 01 00	01 12 05 02	06.76 P>0.05 (N.S)
5	Experience a) 1 to 5 years b) 6 to 10 years c) More than 10 years	- - -	01 02 02	04 16 05	1.15 P>0.05 (N.S)
6	Previous exposure to continuing education program regarding complementary therapies for labour pain Yes No	- -	00 10	02 18	1.07 P>0.05 (N.S)

4. Discussion

Table 4 represent that comparing the total level of knowledge between pretest and posttest the difference mean value was 9.90 with a standard deviation of 4.49 and calculated t value was 12.05.it was statistically significant at P<0.05 level. Hence the structured teaching program is effective to enhance the knowledge of Staff Nurses on complementary therapies on labour pain. The result of the study is supported by Dayana (2025) in her pre experimental design effectiveness of structured teaching program on knowledge of natural pain relief method during labour among

primigravida mothers. The result shows that the pretest and posttest mean difference value was 10.48 and the calculated t value was 14.6 [7] .by comparing the results of both studies there is more evidence that structured teaching program is effective in imparting knowledge.

5. Conclusion

The result of the study concludes that the structured teaching program was effective in enhancing the knowledge of staff Nurses regarding complementary therapies for labour pain.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of ethical approval

- Research approval has taken from the institutional research committee. The present research work does not contain any studies performed on animal/humans subjects by any of the authors
- Permission has taken from the hospital before conducting the study and informed consent was obtained from all the participants included in the study.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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